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Bed shear stress prediction of large-scale waterways using convolutional neural network

Zexia Zhang^a, Ali Khosronejad^a

^aCivil Engineering Department, College of Engineering & Applied Sciences, Stony Brook University, Stony Brook, NY 11794

Abstract

Accurate prediction of bed shear stress is important for analyzing sediment transport and turbine-sediment interactions in large-scale waterways. However, high-fidelity simulations for sediment transport prediction are computationally expensive due to the costly two-way coupling between fluid dynamics and morphodynamics, as well as the time required for bed morphology convergence. To overcome these challenges, we propose a convolutional neural network (CNN) autoencoder algorithm that predicts time-averaged bed shear stress with significantly reduced computational cost compared to high-fidelity simulations.

Keywords: Shear stress; Convolutional neural network; Meandering river; Computational fluid dynamics

1. Introduction

In erodible channel environments, the interaction between a marine hydrokinetic (MHK) device and the evolution of the bed topography could cause the structural failure of the device support structure and the propagation of scour or deposition features within the channel. Therefore, the assessment of sediment transport and turbine-sediment interactions in large-scale waterways is a key environmental issue. However, high-fidelity simulations for sediment transport prediction are computationally expensive due to the costly two-way coupling between fluid dynamics and morphodynamics. In this study, we developed and evaluated the performance of a CNN autoencoder algorithm in predicting the bed shear stress distribution using erodible large-scale virtual meandering rivers of different geometries. The CNN algorithm utilizes instantaneous shear stress of high-fidelity simulation results, along with geometry information as inputs to predict time-averaged shear stress in the eroded large-scale meandering rivers. The results demonstrated the feasibility, accuracy and great efficiency of the proposed CNN algorithm.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study cases

To examine the performance of CNN autoencoder in predicting bed shear stress distribution in large-scale waterways, turbulent flow coupled with sediment transport in ten virtual meandering rivers are considered, as shown in figure 1. The rivers are 2110~4580 m in length, 100 m in width, and 3.3 m in depth. Flows are from left to right. Turbulent flow field and bed shear stress distribution data are calculated using the in-house LES code [1]. In the examination of the proposed CNN autoencoder algorithm, the simulation results of river 1~5 were used to train the CNN, and river 6~10 were used to validate the performance of the trained model.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the virtual meandering rivers used for the training and validation of CNN autoencoder. River 1~5 are the training cases. River 6~10 are validation cases.

2.2. Hydrodynamics and morphodynamics simulation

In this study, the hydrodynamics of the meandering rivers are solved using the three-dimensional (3D), incompressible, spatially averaged continuity and Navier-Stokes equations in curvilinear coordinates [1], i.e., large eddy simulation (LES). The temporal variation in bed elevation is governed by the non-equilibrium equation for sediment mass balance, i.e., Exner-Polya equation. The sediment concentration is simulated using a convection-diffusion equation of passive tracer in [1]. The coupling between the turbulent flow and morphodynamics simulations was performed using the partitioned loose-coupling fluid-structure interaction (FSI) method [1].

During the simulation, LES of turbulent flow in meandering rivers were initially conducted to generate converged turbulent flow fields. Subsequently, LES coupled with morphodynamic simulations were performed to predict equilibrium and time-averaged bed morphology and shear stress.

2.3. Convolutional neural network autoencoder

The autoencoder CNN model composed of eight convolutional layers was used to reconstruct the bed shear stress distribution. The inputs include the instantaneous shear stress distribution obtained from the hydrodynamic simulation, and the geometry information of the meandering rivers (streamwise coordinate, spanwise coordinate, and local curvature). The output is the time-averaged shear stress. The CNN was trained using 5 rivers, and input instantaneous shear stress in 5 different time-steps, leading to 25 training samples in total. The training used 1000 epochs to converge in 2 CPU hours. Then the trained model is validated using river 6~10.

3. Results and discussion

The comparison of time-averaged shear stress distribution between LES and CNN predictions are shown in figure 2. For brevity, only two of the validation cases are presented here. The results indicate that the trained CNN model can reconstruct the time-averaged shear stress distribution in different geometry of meandering rivers. The relative prediction error is below 10% in most area. At the bending area where the shear stress distribution has a large gradient, the relative error is below 30%.

In high-fidelity simulation approach, the LES need to be first conducted to generate converged turbulence flow field, then to couple with sediment transport and morphodynamics simulation to predict shear stress distribution in equilibrium bed morphology. The first step will take ~ 3000 CPU hours for each of the meandering river, and the second step will take $\sim 5 \times 10^5$ CPU hours. However, since the proposed CNN algorithm only requires the results of

the first step as the input, and the inference cost is 1 CPU second, the total cost of the trained CNN model to predict the shear stress in a new river geometry is <1% of the high-fidelity simulation approach.

Fig. 2. Comparison of shear stress distribution between LES and CNN predictions. (a) is river 6; (b) is river 8.

4. Conclusions

This study presents a CNN autoencoder algorithm for the efficient and accurate prediction of bed shear stress in large-scale meandering rivers. The implemented algorithm demonstrates its potential to significantly reduce computational costs while maintaining reliable predictions. This approach holds promise for future studies investigating turbine-sediment interactions and other applications in engineering design and environmental management of large-scale tidal farms.

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References

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